

Use of Potassium Bromate : Syntheses of Iodoxybenzene Derivatives

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Synthesis of iodoxy compounds by the oxidation of various iodobenzene derivatives using potassium bromate under acidic condition have been discussed.

WITH a view to preparing iodoxybenzene in large quantity and investigate its suitability as an oxidising agent for various organic compounds, potassium bromate and dilute sulphuric acid were used to oxidise iodobenzene at elevated temperature. The reported method of Lucas and Kennedy¹ for the preparation of iodoxybenzene from iodobenzene proved to be lengthy and irksome in our hands while that of Sharefkin and Saltzman² was neither economical nor free from danger for the use of peracetic acid though the yield of the desired product in this single step reaction was excellent. Other effective oxidising agents employed are oxygen³, perbenzoic acid⁴ and potassium peroxy-monosulphate⁵. The use of dibenzoyl peroxide and iodine has been reported by Erlenmeyer⁶. Recently Yagupolski, Maletina, Kondratenko and Orda⁷ reported the preparation of iodylarenes from iodoarenes using nitric acid and trifluoroacetic anhydride followed by hydrolysis of the intermediate *bis*-(trifluoroacetoxy)-iodoarenes.

It has been noted⁸ that the potassium bromate exhibited oxidising action only with acetic acid under refluxing condition but displayed both oxidising as well as brominating capabilities when dilute (4-8 N) sulphuric acid was employed. When a mixture of acetic acid, iodobenzene and potassium bromate was heated under reflux for one and a half hours, no desired product could be isolated, and the starting material was recovered unchanged. However, when an aqueous solution of potassium bromate was rapidly added to the boiling mixture of iodobenzene and sulphuric acid (8N) with subsequent boiling for one and a half hours, a crystalline iodoxybenzene was separated. The reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and the residue was washed with chloroform to furnish silky white desired product in nearly 50% yield, m.p. 222° (explosion)². It exhibited the characteristic four ir bands of iodoxybenzene⁷ at 771, 758, 730 and 712 cm⁻¹. Bell and Morgan⁹ reported the absence of characteristic bands in the ir spectrum of iodobenzene between 700-900 cm⁻¹ while the iodoxybenzene exhibited the three characteristic bands at 720±5, 745±5 and 765±5 cm⁻¹. However, *O*-iodoxynitrobenzene and *O*-iodoxybenzoic acid failed to show these bands

possibly due to interaction of the two bulky groups. Our product had a purity of 96% as determined by iodometry¹⁰ and it did not liberate iodine from potassium iodide in saturated sodium borate solution indicating the absence of iodobenzene¹⁰. This test for iodobenzene derivatives and the sodium fusion test for heteroelements (confirmed by generation of the elemental halogens from the sodium fusion extract and testing them successively with alcoholic solution of fluorescein, starch-iodide and starch paper, nitrogen in the sample never interfered) were performed as the routine analysis of all the iodoxy compounds described. The elemental analysis could not be furnished due to the explosive nature and consequently, its structure has been established through the identical ir spectrum with the freshly prepared authentic iodoxybenzene¹. Also this material was reduced with potassium iodide in acidic solution and the product, thus obtained, was identical with the ir spectrum of the authentic iodobenzene. It was observed that the iodoxybenzene was decomposed fast in acidic mixture by potassium bromide, hence a little excess of potassium bromate was used. From the mother liquor of the above filtration, 1-bromo-4-iodobenzene¹¹, m.p. 88°, (2%) and unreacted iodobenzene (25%), were isolated by usual work up.

Good yields of 1-bromo-4-iodoxybenzene¹², 1-iodoxy-4-nitrobenzene⁹, 2-iodoxybenzoic acid¹² and 1-iodoxy-3-nitrobenzene⁹ were obtained by similar oxidation of 1-bromo-4-iodobenzene, 1-iodo-4-nitrobenzene, 2-iodobenzoic acid and 1-iodo-3-nitrobenzene respectively. However, in case of 3-iodotoluene, 3-iodoxytoluene² was obtained in poor yield, possibly due to the side reactions like bromination of the benzene ring or oxidation of the methyl group. Ring-deactivators on iodobenzene favoured the oxidation of iodine to pentavalent stage while ring-activators (as in iodotoluene) made the oxidation more complicated either by involving a substantial amount of bromination of the benzene nucleus or by simultaneous oxidation of the ring-activators themselves. Potassium bromate and dilute sulphuric acid produced iodoxybenzene from iodobenzene in excellent yields. Willgerodt¹⁴

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oxidised iodosobenzene using either bromine and caustic soda or hypochlorous acid.

Experimental

A.R. acetic acid was heated under reflux with excess of potassium dichromate for six hrs and distilled just before use. Pure potassium bromate, sulphuric acid and distilled water were used whenever needed. Ir spectra were taken in Nujol in Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer (297).

Iodoxybenzene and 1-bromo-4-iodobenzene : (a) To the boiling mixture of iodobenzene (40.8 g) and sulphuric acid (8*N*; 280 ml) was added a solution of potassium bromate (26.8 g in 280 ml of warm water) from the separatory funnel within twenty minutes. The heating was continued for one and a half hrs, and the reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature, filtered and the brown residue was washed successively with water and chloroform to furnish colourless crystalline iodoxybenzene (21.5 g; 45%), m.p. 222° (explosion). The ir spectrum of the authentic iodoxybenzene¹ was superimposable with this product exhibiting the characteristic bands^{7,9} at 771, 758, 730 and 712 cm⁻¹ along with 1460, 1441, 1377, 1170, 1044, 990 and 678 cm⁻¹. It had a purity of 96% as evident from iodometric estimation¹⁰ and the product isolated from this estimation exhibited identical ir spectrum with authentic iodobenzene. Prolonging reaction time did not improve the yield of iodoxybenzene. The mother liquor of the above filtration on work up with chloroform furnished 1-bromo-4-iodobenzene¹¹, m.p. 88° (0.7 g; 2%) and unreacted iodobenzene, b.p. 175-180° (10.2 g; 25%). (b) To the boiling mixture of iodobenzene (10.2 g) and glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was added a solution of potassium bromate (6.7 g in 65 ml of warm water) and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for ninety minutes. On work up in the usual way, the unreacted iodobenzene, b.p. 175-180° (8.5 g) was obtained together with a very small amount of iodoxybenzene. (c) The above experiment when carried out with glacial acetic acid (15 ml), iodobenzene (2.0 g) and potassium bromate (1.4 g) only the starting material was recovered unchanged.

1-Bromo-4-iodoxybenzene : To the boiling solution of 1-bromo-4-iodobenzene (2.8 g), acetic acid (50 ml) and sulphuric acid (8*N*; 15 ml) was added a solution of potassium bromate (1.3 g in 15 ml of warm water) from the dropping funnel within five minutes. The evolution of bromine was noted with simultaneous separation of the solid material. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured onto 200 ml of ice-water, filtered and the residue was washed successively with water and chloroform. The silver-white iodoxy compound (3.1 g, 98%), m.p. 228° (explosion) exhibited bands at 1553, 1270, 1165, 1061, 1044, 998, 798, 773, 746, 722 and 701 cm⁻¹. It was 96.5% pure. From the product of this estimation was isolated a crystalline material, m.p. 84°, which remained undepressed on admixture with starting material, m.p. 88°, thus establishing the identity of the iodoxy compound.

1-Iodoxy-3-nitrobenzene : To a boiling mixture of 1-iodo-3-nitrobenzene (5.0 g, b.p. 123-124°/1 mm) and sulphuric acid (8*N*; 30 ml) was added potassium bromate (2.7 g in 30 ml of warm water) from dropping funnel within thirty minutes. The heating was continued for further ninety minutes, and the reaction mixture was cooled, filtered, washed, (water and chloroform) to yield the silver-white solid (2.6 g; 46%) m.p. 218° (explosion). It exhibited bands at 1598, 1533, 1349, 1268, 1088, 1049, 997, 889, 861, 802, 767, 728, 718, 710 and 658 cm⁻¹. The filtrate after usual work up furnished the starting material (2.65 g) characterised through identical ir spectra. The product was found to be of 96% purity and from this estimation was isolated 1-iodo-3-nitrobenzene.

1-Iodoxy-4-nitrobenzene : In a similar way a mixture of 1-iodo-4-nitrobenzene (10 g), sulphuric acid (8*N*; 100 ml) and potassium bromate (10 g in 100 ml of warm water) furnished 1-iodoxy-4-nitrobenzene (10 g; 88%, m.p. 212°, explosion) which exhibited ir absorption at 1602, 1531, 1352, 1310, 1040, 850, 840, 773, 750, 735, 723, 705 and 670 cm⁻¹. The purity of the product was found to be 90% on iodometric analysis¹⁰ and from the titrated mixture was isolated a product (25 mg), m.p. 168°, which was found to be 1-iodo-4-nitrobenzene¹² through mixed m.p. with the starting material, identical ir spectra exhibiting bands at 1595, 1570, 1375, 1352, 1340, 1310, 1180, 1108, 1052, 1010, 852, 838, 735 and 675 cm⁻¹ and the mass spectrometry indicating major signals at m/e 249 (M⁺), 219 (M - NO) 203 (M - NO₂) and 191 M - (NO + CO).

2-Iodoxybenzoic acid : A mixture of 2-iodobenzoic acid (13.5 g), sulphuric acid (8*N*; 85 ml), acetic acid (50 ml) and potassium bromate (8.4 g in 85 ml of warm water) furnished in a similar method silver-white crystalline desired compound (14.5 g; 95%), m.p. 222° (explosion) which was free from iodoso compound and exhibited peaks at 1610, 1562, 1378, 1341, 1302, 1150, 1019, 836, 747, 697 and 650 cm⁻¹. It had a purity of 92% as determined iodometrically¹⁰ and the neutral equivalent (N.E.) was found to be 278 ± 5. The starting material indicated bands at 1678, 1582, 1560, 1432, 1401, 1378, 1296, 1268, 1150, 1110, 1066, 1045, 1016, 957, 808, 797, 740, 680 and 637 cm⁻¹.

Oxidation of 3-iodotoluene with potassium bromate : In a similar method a mixture of 3-iodotoluene (3.2 g), sulphuric acid (8*N*; 55 ml) and potassium bromate (5.2 g in 55 ml of warm water) furnished a white amorphous product (1.5 g), m.p. 190° (d, no explosion). This material contained iodoso derivative¹⁰, hence it was reoxidised with potassium bromate (0.6 g in 10 ml of water) and sulphuric acid (8*N*; 10 ml) in the usual way. The final product (1.2 g) was purified from the adhering iodoso compound by treatment with potassium iodide in saturated solution of borax¹⁰ followed by filtration and washing with water and chloroform. The air-dried white amorphous residue (0.8 g), thus obtained, melted at 198° (explosion) and exhibited bands at 1022, 808, 772, 749, 717 and 677 cm⁻¹. It was of 70% purity as determined

iodometrically (calculated on the basis of iodoxytoluene). From the reaction mixture of this estimation was isolated a product by the usual work up which evaporatively distilled at 60-70°/5 mm. The mass spectrum of this sample indicated signals at m/e 218 and 91 (M^+ and $M-I$ respectively for iodotoluene), 296, 298 (M^+ for bromiodotoluene), 269, 271, ($M'-I$), 217 ($M'-Br$), 374, 376, 378 (M''^+ for dibromiodotoluene) 295, 297 ($M''-Br$), 168, 170 ($M''-Br-I$), 247, 249, 251 ($M''-I$). These data clearly indicated that a mixture of products was formed during the oxidation of 3-iodotoluene.

Oxidation of iodosobenzene with potassium bromate: (a) To a boiling mixture of iodosobenzene¹ (1.2 g; 80% pure) and sulphuric acid (8N, 25 ml) was added dropwise a solution of potassium bromate (1.8 g in 25 ml of warm water) in course of twenty minutes. There was evolution of bromine vapours and the mixture was heated under reflux for a period of one and a half hours. On cooling, the reaction mixture deposited large amount of colourless solid which was filtered and washed successively with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, water and ethanol. The air dried sample (1.0 g, m.p. 223°, explosion) did not develop any blue colour with potassium iodide in a saturated aqueous solution of borax containing starch¹⁰ indicating the absence of unreacted iodosobenzene in the product. The ir spectrum of this material was identical with that of authentic iodoxybenzene reported¹ earlier. It was found to be 96% pure¹⁰. (b) A mixture of iodosobenzene (2.2 g), potassium bromate (3.3 g) and glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was heated under reflux for ninety minutes. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into water and the solid separated, was filtered, washed and dried as in (a) to furnish a crystalline solid (20 mg, m.p. 230°, explosion) which did not respond to the test for iodoso compounds¹⁰.

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